

Tallis and Kaniadakis Entropy Densities as h-Derivatives and a Link to $\ln q$ or $\ln k$

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In (1), it is argued that Tallis and Kaniadakis entropy densities may be expressed in terms of finite h-derivatives. It is suggested that this is a way of generally describing these new entropies. Here we try to argue that this idea seems to be linked to the forms $\ln q(p) = -e_i/T$ (Tsallis case) and $\ln k(p) = -e_i/T$ (Kaniadakis case). This, in turn, follows from two conditions. The first is that p be a power law distribution in both cases and the second, that it become the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for a certain limit of the power.

MB, Tsallis and Kaniadakis $\ln(p)$, $\ln q(p)$, $\ln k(p)$

The three above distributions all have the following function in common:

$$\ln(p) = -e_i/T \text{ (MB)} \quad \ln q(p) = -e_i/T \text{ (Tsallis)} \quad \text{and} \quad \ln k(p) = -e_i/T \text{ (Kaniadakis)} \quad ((1))$$

Clearly, \ln , $\ln q$ and $\ln k$ are inverse functions of p , but more generally, we argue that ((1)) holds because one has:

$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ ((2)) and must have a corresponding:

$$\exp(C \ln(h(p(e_1))) \exp(C \ln(h(p(e_2)))) = \exp(C \ln(h(p(e_3))) \exp(C \ln(h(p(e_4)))) \quad ((3))$$

In other words, even though the different distributions are complicated, the notion of conservation of energy ((2)) must remain in all cases.

We argue that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis distributions are created a priori with two key features.

- (A) $p(e_i)$ must be a power law (based on a single parameter)
- (B) In a certain limit of a parameter linked to the power, one must retrieve the MB results.

This seems to suggest that $\ln q$ and $\ln k$ must contain $p(e_i)$ to powers linked to only one parameter if $\ln q$ and $\ln k$ are to be inverses of $p(e_i)$ which is a power law.

Considering Power Laws

The next step is to consider how to link $\ln(p)$ to a power p power x .

$$\text{Exp}\{ x \ln(p) \} = p \text{ power } x \quad ((4))$$

If one wishes to create a function $h(p)$ which becomes $\ln(p)$ for $x \rightarrow 0$, then there are two immediate possibilities:

$$\{1 - \exp(x \ln(p))\} / x \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{or} \quad \{\exp(x \ln(p)) - \exp(-x \ln(p))\} / 2x \quad ((5b))$$

The first result ultimately leads to the Tsallis case, and the second, to the Kaniadakis. We note here that in the limit $x \rightarrow 0$, one has $0/0$ and so must use l'Hopital's rule to find $\ln(p)$. The idea of a derivative appearing may already be anticipated from the form ((4)).

The above forms ((5a)) and ((5b)), however, apply to $h(p)$ (i.e. $\ln q(p)$ and $\ln k(p)$) and not entropy. It is not even clear how to create an entropy expression given ((5a)), ((5b)).

A key point we note, however, is that ((5a)) and ((5b)) become $\ln(p)$ through l'Hopital's rule, i.e. the denominator tends to zero when $x \rightarrow 0$. The Maxwell-Boltzmann entropy is:

$$-\text{Sum over } i \quad p(e_i) \ln(p(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

It is known that $\ln(p(e_i))$ is linked with $\ln q(p)$ and $\ln k(p)$ and these both have a denominator which tends to 0 when $q \rightarrow 0$, $k \rightarrow 0$, and so one would expect that $\ln q(p)$ and $\ln k(p)$ would be part of the entropy expression. It is, however, not clear what should replace $p(e_i)$ (if anything). In the $q \rightarrow 0$, $k \rightarrow 0$ limit, the entire entropy should also be of the form $0/0$ and l'Hopital's rule (due to the 0 denominator of the $\ln q$ or $\ln k$ term). Thus, we argue that the forms $\ln q(p)$ and $\ln k(p)$ are the driving forms in this h-derivative approach. This means that the numerator of the entropies must also tend to 0, just like the numerators of $\ln q(p)$, $\ln k(p)$. The question now becomes: What is the form of the numerators of S_q and S_k , the entropy densities?

A Priori Method of Finding the Entropy

Shannon's entropy is the average of the information $\ln(p(e_i)) = -e_i/T$. The Tsallis and Kaniadakis approaches retain the notion of information as $-e_i/T$ with one using $\ln q(p)$ and the other, $\ln k(p)$. The question is: Does one replace the $p(e_i)$ factor of $\ln(p(e_i))$ in ((6)) and if so why?

If one considers the forms for $\ln q$ and $\ln k$, i.e. ((5a)) and ((5b)), then:

$$\text{Tsallis case: } \ln q(p) = 1/(1-q) \{ 1 - (1-q) p^{1-q} \} \quad \text{with } q \rightarrow 0 \text{ yielding the MB result } ((7a))$$

$$\text{and Kaniadakis case: } \ln k = 1/(2k) \{ p^k - p^{-k} \} \quad ((7b)) \text{ with } k \rightarrow 0 \text{ yielding the MB case}$$

Given that $\ln k$ is the inverse of $p(e_i)$, one may show that in the Kaniadakis case one has:

$$p(e_i) = \exp_k(x) = \{\sqrt{1+kx} + kx\}^{1/k} \quad \text{where } x = -e_i/T \quad ((8))$$

Then $p(e_i)p(-e_i) = 1$, just like the MB case and one has probability linked directly to energy e_i , so the constraint in question is: $\text{Sum over } i \quad e_i p(e_i) = E_{\text{ave}}$. Thus, the $p(e_i)$ factor in ((6)) should remain for the Kaniadakis case. (2) shows that one considers the unnormalized case.

If one solves for the Tsallis $p(e_i)$ one finds: $p(x) = \{1+(1-q)x\}^{1/(1-q)}$ ((9))

This does not satisfy $p(x)p(-x)=1$, where $x=-e_i/T$ and so one cannot use $p(e_i)$ in ((6)). A different form is needed and must physically represent the probability associated with e_i . We suggest that one use $p(e_i)$ power q (as one is dealing with a power law and this is a physical expression).

In such cases, one may show that both the Tsallis and Kaniadakis entropy densities do both have the form of a finite derivative as described in (1). In particular:

$$S_q = \{1 - \sum_i p(e_i)^q\} / (1-q) \quad ((10))$$

If $h=1-q$ and h is the finite change parameter, then S_q is of the form of $D(h) \{1 - \sum_i p(e_i)^q\}$, where the power q in ((10)) = $1+h$. In other words. $p(e_i)$ in the first term is to the power 1 because $1 = \sum_i p(e_i)$ and in the second, to $p(e_i)$ power $1+h$, with h in the denominator. Hence a finite derivative form exists.

In the Kaniadakis case, entropy density should be (see (2)):

$$S_k = \sum_i \frac{1}{(2k)} \{ p(e_i)^{1+k} - p(e_i)^{1-k} \} \quad ((11))$$

Setting $k=h$, one has the form of a finite derivative, but this time one does not use $f(x)$ and $f(x+h)$, but $f(x+h)$ and $f(x-h)$ as discussed in (1).

Using the Finite Derivative Approach to Determine the form of $p(e_i)$ in the Entropy Density

Although the approach in the above section does allow one to a priori seek $p(e_i)$ power q as linked with the Tsallis situation and $p(e_i)$, with the Kaniadakis, the suggestion of (1) that the finite derivative describes both forms seems to be interesting in that if it is taken to hold a priori, then one would need no extra arguments to link p power q with the Tsallis case and p with the Kaniadakis. The requirement of a finite derivative form for the respective entropy densities would automatically suggest that:

$p(e_i)$ power q is used with $\ln_q(p)$ in ((6)) for the Tsallis case ((12a)) and

$p(e_i)$ is used with $\ln_k(p)$ in ((6)) for the Kaniadakis case ((12b)).

Thus, the finite derivative form applied to entropy densities seems to be an interesting defining idea, as suggested in (1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, (1) suggests that the Tsallis and Kaniadakis entropy densities may be described in terms of finite derivatives. We argue that this interesting result seems to follow from an inverse function of $p(e_i)$ having a power law form if $p(e_i)$ itself has a power law form (based on a single parameter) (although the powers of the two are reciprocals). If one further wishes to have a single power law parameter which, in a limiting case, makes the inverse of $p(e_i)$ become $\ln(p)$ (the MB result), then we show that there are two results, one for the Tsallis case and the other, for the Kaniadakis. We argue that one must have a l'Hopital's Rule situation if the parameter is set to 0 and show that the entropy density should also have this feature. If the entropy includes a factor $h(p(e_i))$ where h is the inverse of p , one may then induce the form of the function of $p(e_i)$ which multiplies $h(p(e_i))$. In the limit of the parameter becoming 0, this function must become $p(e_i)$ (the MB case). We show that this then leads to a finite derivative form.

References

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